

Contribution to the knowledge of the Asiatic *Amphipyra* Ochsenheimer, 1816 with the description of four new species and one new subspecies (Noctuidae, Amphipyrinae Guenee, 1837)

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Abstract. Description of four new species and one new subspecies of *Amphipyra* Ochsenheimer, 1816 is provided with 22 adult images and 31 genitalia figures.

Keywords. *Amphipyra*, new description, taxonomy, Asia.

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Introduction

The most recent publication on the genus *Amphipyra* Ochsenheimer, 1816 by Ronkay et al. (2023), gives the diagnosis of altogether six new species and a new subspecies, as well as revises the status of a taxon and designates a lectotype. The author of the present paper carefully studied his own vast *Amphipyra* material, during which, in addition to those mentioned in the publication cited above, he managed to establish the existence of four additional species and one subspecies of *Amphipyra* that are new to science. Below are descriptions of the new taxa, with color and genitalia images. Unfortunately, most of the species are very local or rare, in some cases they are only known from one or a few specimens and it was possible to study a large series of only a few of them. It is worth mentioning that most of the taxa within this genus are very similar to each other in their external features (different shades of the brownish or greyish ground color of forewings only, and very simple forewing pattern of dorsal forewing surface) and also in male and female genitalia configuration. The best keys for a positive determination of the males are the size and shape of the uncus and the configuration of the vesica (number, arrangement and size of the diverticuli, cornuti, plates and scobination). In females, the shape of the ductus bursae and the appendix and corpus bursae are the most worthy of study.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein: HM = genitalia slide of Márton Hreblay; HMB = collection of Márton Hreblay in HNHM (Budapest, Hungary); HNHM = Hungarian Natural History Museum (Budapest, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide of Péter Gyulai; PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); RL = genitalia slide of László Ronkay; ZFMK = Zoologisches Forschungsmuseum Alexander Koenig (Zoological Research Museum Alexander Koenig), (Bonn, Germany); m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype; prov. = province.

The type material of *Amphipyra charon* Draudt, 1950 is deposited in ZFMK, while all of the types and figured specimens are deposited in the collection of the author.

Descriptions of the new taxa

***Amphipyra huilini* sp. n.** (Figs 1, 23, 24)

Holotype. Male, “CHINA, Prov. Sichuan, Ching-cheng Shan, 1500-1800 m, 31°12' N, 102°47' E, 1-30. IX. 2006, leg. V. Siniaev & Team“, slide no. GYP 5953 (deposited in PGM).

Diagnosis. The new species (Fig. 1) is the sister species of the Indo-Chinese *Amphipyra owaadai* Hreblay, Peregovits & Ronkay, 1999 and of the Chinese *Amphipyra joelmineti* L. Ron-

kay & G. Ronkay, 2023 (Fig. 2). It is the smallest species among the three relative taxa; its wingspan 45 mm, while *Amphipyra joelmineti* 53–58 mm and *A. o. owadai* is 61–63 mm, and the specimens of ssp. *nepalensis* are 53–59 mm. Besides the significantly smaller size, *Amphipyra huilini* sp. n. can be distinguished from *A. o. owadai* and the ssp. *nepalensis* (figured in Ronkay & Ronkay, 2023) by its unicolorous dark brown forewings, without wing pattern; from the most similar *A. joelmineti* by its less elongated forewings and the much more reddish hindwings. The male genitalia of *A. huilini* sp. n. (Figs 23, 24) conspicuously differ from the most similar *A. joelmineti* (Figs 25, 26) and that of the less resembling further two relative taxa by the broadly rounded (and not angular) medial section of the dorsal side of the valvae, the reduced left one and the very small thorn-like right one of the two asymmetrical saccular processes, which are much longer and differently shaped in the three relative taxa.

Description. Wingspan 45 mm. Antennae filiform. Head and thorax dark brown. Forewing mono-chromatic shining dark brown, almost black, without any of visible wing pattern; fringe like the ground color. Hindwing dark red, with a dark brown wedge-like field in the fore section, broadening towards the margin. Wing pattern absent, fringe pale reddish. Underside of wings shining, slightly paler in colour than upperside.

Male genitalia (Figs 23, 24) can be characterized by the long and strong uncus, terminated with an elongated thorn; subquadrangular, dorsally extended juxta; long, v-shaped vinculum; broad valvae, broadly rounded medial section of dorsal side of valvae, with a regressed and not prominent left saccular process and a very small thorn-like right one. Aedeagus strong, with a long, strongly sclerotised carinal plate. Vesica tube having a small prominence dorsally and a row of small cornuti with almost the same size basally; subbasally armed with a row of somewhat larger ones, continuing medially with some very long and strong ones sitting on a broad sclerotized base. The cornuti field terminated with some strong sclerotized bars.

Distribution. The new species is known from Central China (Prov. Sichuan).

Etymology. The new species is dedicated to Mr. Han Hui Lin (Harbin, China), a specialist of the Asiatic Noctuidae.

***Amphipyra perflua sichuana* ssp. n.** (Figs 3, 4, 27, 28, 29, 30, 43)

Holotype. male, “CHINA, prov. Sichuan, SW of Heishui, 3100 m, 320031°N, 1030151° E, 4-8. VIII. 2012, leg. M. Murzin“, slide no. GYP 5947 (deposited in PGM).

Paratypes. 5 males, 3 females, “CHINA, prov. Gansu, 2350 m, Min Shan, 50 km W of Wudu, 33°30' N, 104°35' E, 27. VII.-14. VIII. 2000, leg. Plutenko & Siniaev“ (PGM); slide nos.: GYP 5975 (male), 5959 (female).

Diagnosis and description. *Amphipyra perflua* (Fabricius, 1787) (Figs 5, 6) is a widely distributed Transpalaeartic species. The southern-easternmost populations in central and southern China (Figs 3, 4) are similar both in the external and genitalia features to the nominotypical subspecies, however somewhat differ from the nominotypical subspecies by in average larger size (49–57 mm and 44–50 mm, respectively). The best character for separation (besides the very different geographical distribution pattern) in the external features is the end of the postmedial line; it ends perpendicular on the inner edge of the forewing in the nominotypical subspecies, while oblique in the new subspecies. In the male genitalia of the new subspecies (Figs 27, 28, 29, 30) the cornuti of the bundle in the vesica is longer than in the nominotypical subspecies (Figs 31, 32). In the female genitalia, the shape of the antrum plate is very variable in both taxa, but of the new subspecies the ductus bursae and the corpus bursae are longer than in the nominotypical one (Figs 43 and 44).

Distribution and biology. The new subspecies is known from the provinces of Sichuan and Gansu in China. It occurs at higher altitudes in late summer.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is after the province of the holotype locality.

***Amphipyra yunnannocturna* sp. n.** (Figs 7, 8, 9, 12, 33, 34, 45, 46)

Holotype. female, China, N Yunnan, Diqing Tibetan Aut. Pref., 5 km SE of Deqin, 3356 m, 19. VI. 2009, leg. B. Benedek, GYP 5936 (deposited in PGM).

Paratypes. 2 males, with the same data as of the holotype. (PGM); 1 male, with the same data as of the holotype, but with the date 19. VI. 2009. (PGM); 2 females, China, prov. Sichuan,

env. Shade, (N of Jiulong), 3400 m, 19-21. VIII. 2007, leg. S. Murzin (PGM); slide nos.: RL 9977 (male), GYP 5937 (female).

Diagnosis. The most similar, close relative of *Amphipyra yunnannocturna* **sp. n.** (Figs 7, 8, 9, 12) is *Amphipyra charon* Draudt, 1950 (Figs 10, 11), but the new species has a much darker ground color of the wings without the red-brown suffusion and lacks or almost lacks the conspicuous diffuse light shade on the outer edge of the transverse lines, particularly on the subterminal line, compared to *A. charon*. No male genitalia figure was available from the closely related species *A. charon*, since the entire type series consists of only female individuals, so a diagnostic comparison of the male genitalia was not possible.

It is very easy to distinguish the female genitalia of the new species (Figs 45, 46), from those of *A. charon* (Fig. 47), since *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.** has much shorter ductus bursae, much smaller appendix bursae and longer, more elongated corpus bursae.

Description. (Figs 7, 8, 9, 12) Medium-sized species, with a wingspan of 37–44 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Head and thorax dark brown. Forewing monochromatic dark brown, slightly shining. Wing pattern not conspicuous, pale brownish; only the sinuous, zig-zagging antemedial and postmedial transverse lines and the orbicular spot being well visible. Hindwing light unicolorous brown, with obscure darker discal spot, marginal area with broad, slightly darker suffusion. Underside of the wings shining, and brownish, inner costal area of forewing and of hindwing much lighter. The diffuse shade of the postmedial line in the forewing and of the medial line in the hindwing well visible.

Male genitalia (Figs 33, 34). Uncus very long, almost evenly broad, apically with a tiny horn. Vinculum long, v-shaped. Valva elongated, straight, slightly broaden distally, cucullus section asymmetrically rounded terminally. Aedeagus broad, straight, ventral carinal bar long, slim, and strongly sclerotized. Vesica recurved dorsad, broad, bear about ten strong, shortly conical cornuti sitting on a broad base distally and subterminally.

Female genitalia. (Figs 45, 46). Papillae anales elongate, apically rounded. Apophyses posteriores and anteriores very long and slim, the apophyses anteriores shorter. Antrum funnel-like. Ductus bursae long, tubular. Appendix bursae small, terminally rounded. Corpus bursae elongated-saccate, tapering in the long medial section, while much broader anteriorly and enlarged terminally.

Distribution and biology. The new species is known only from the Chinese provinces Yunnan and Sichuan, above 3000 m.

Etymology. The name of the new species refers to the discovery of the first specimens in the province of Yunnan by night.

***Amphipyra meridionalis* sp. n.** (Figs 13, 14, 15, 35, 36, 48, 49)

Holotype. male, “IRAN, prov. Boyerahmad-va- Kohgiluyeh, SE- Zagros, 3000 m, Kuh-e-Dena, n. Bijan pass, 6 km N of Cisakht; 5 - 6. VI. 2005, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai“, slide no. GYP 2370 (deposited in PGM).

Paratypes. 1male, IRAN, prov. Boyerahmad-va- Kohgiluyeh, SE- Zagros, 3000 m., Kuh-e-Dena, n. Bijan pass, 6 km N of Cisakht; 8 - 9. X. 2002, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 female, same data, but 10-11. V. 2002, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 2 males, IRAN, prov. Boyerahmad-va-Kohgiluyeh, SE- Zagros, Kuh-e-Dena, 2450 m, 5 km SW of Sisakht, 04 - 05. VI. 2005, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, 1 female, IRAN, prov. Boyerahmad-va-Kohgiluyeh, SE- Zagros, 3000 m, Kuh-e-Dena, n. Bijan pass, 6 km N of Sisakht, 13 - 14. VII. 2010, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, IRAN, prov. Esfahan, C - Zagros, 2600 m, 2 km NE of Semirom, 05 - 10. V. 2002, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 2 males, IRAN, prov. Esfahan, C - Zagros, 2600 m, 2 km NE of Semirom, 03 - 04. VI. 2005, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, IRAN, prov. Busher, S - Zagros, 400 m, near Dalekhi, 24. - 25. X. 2003, leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); 1 male, IRAN, prov. Fars, S - Zagros, 7 km N of Sivand; 9 - 10. VI. 2003. leg. P. Gyulai & A. Garai (PGM); slide nos.: GYP 1859, 2029, 2120, 2530, 2723 (males), 2567, 5938 (females).

Diagnosis. The closest relatives of the new species (Figs 13, 14, 15) are *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759) (Figs 16, 17), and *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888 (Figs 20, 21), however, *A. meridionalis* is rather resembling to the former one in the external features, while more similar to

the second species in the male genitalia features, whereas the new species has individual features in the female genitalia. *Amphipyra meridionalis* **sp. n.** (Figs 13, 14, 15) can be separated from both known species with its lighter, shining greyish suffused forewings with the sinuous, ribbon-like, conspicuously darker, greyish-brown subterminal field and the lighter, greyish suffused hindwings. In the male genitalia, the new species (Figs 35, 36) differs from *A. turcomana* (Figs 41, 42) in its medially more tapering valvae with less broad cucullus, shorter uncus, longer dorsal medial extension of the deltoid juxta, and the much less ample terminal diverticulum with a denser cover of short, hair-like spiculi and a much stronger, longer single spine. The male genitalia of the new species are more distinctive from those of *A. tragopoginis* (Figs 37, 38), having much shorter uncus, less robust, medially more tapering valvae, much longer dorsal medial appendage of the deltoid juxta, much smaller terminal diverticulum of the vesica with a dense cover of short hair-like spiculi (while it is practically naked in *A. tragopoginis*) and the less numerous cornuti and spines are composed in one group (while those are in two groups in *A. tragopoginis*). In the female genitalia, the new species (Figs 48, 49) has calyculate ductus bursae (it is tubular both in *A. tragopoginis* (Fig. 50) and in *A. turcomana* (Figs 52, 53)) and larger appendix bursae than *A. turcomana* (Figs 52, 53) (which has a very small appendix bursae), but smaller than that of *A. tragopoginis* (Fig. 50), being conjoined with the corpus bursae in the whole inner section. Additionally, the corpus bursae of the new species is strongly tapering terminally, while it is broadly rounded in the two relative species. The apophyses anteriores of *A. meridionalis* **sp. n.** are conspicuously longer than in *A. tragopoginis*.

Description. (Figs 13, 14, 15). Medium-sized species, wingspan 30–33 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Head and thorax brown. Forewing monochromatic light shining greyish-brown, suffused with blackish scales. Wing pattern reduced; only the sinuous, ribbon-like, conspicuously darker, greyish-brown subterminal field visible, while orbicular and reniform stigmata present by a single and a double dot. Hindwing light unicolorous greyish brown, with obscure darker discal spot, the marginal area slightly broadly darker and darker suffused; medial line and cilia ochreous. The underside of wings shining, whitish-greyish.

Male genitalia (Figs 35, 36). Uncus long, elongate spatulate. Vinculum rather short, v-shaped. Valva evenly curved dorsad, cucullus strongly broaden and hairy. Juxta deltoid, dorso-medial extension long. Aedeagus broad, curved ventrad, carinal bar broadly sclerotized. Vesica bears two diverticuli, from which the subbasal dorsal one rather small, tongue-like, while the terminal one globular with a dense cover of short, hair-like spiculi and a much stronger, longer single spine.

Female genitalia. (Figs 48, 49). Papillae anales elongate, apically rounded. Apophyses posteriores and anteriores very long and slim, the apophyses anteriores much shorter. Antrum funnel-like. Ductus bursae short, and posteriorly broaden. Appendix bursae long, less prominent, terminally broaden, angular. Corpus bursae elongated-saccate, strongly curved and tapering terminally.

Distribution and biology. The new species is known only from the southern Zagros Mts. in Iran. It occurs mostly in higher altitudes in mid-summer, but appears in the low ranges near the Persian Gulf in autumn. The habitat of the type is shown in fig. 22.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its southern distribution pattern.

***Amphipyra occithianshanica* sp. n.** (Figs 18, 19, 39, 40, 51)

Holotype. male, "USSR, ÜBSSR (Uzbekistan), W Thian-Shan, Chimgan, 800-2000 m, 18-25. 07. 1990, leg. P. Gyulai & M. Hreblay", slide GYP 2121 (deposited in PGM).

Paratypes. 43 males, 11 females, with the same data as of the holotype (PGM); 27 males, 24 females, with the same data as of the holotype (HMB, HNHM); 4 males, 4 females, with the same data as of the holotype (HNHM); slide nos.: GYP 5991(male), 5977 (female).

Diagnosis. The closest relatives of the new species (Figs 18, 19) are *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759) (Figs 16, 17) and *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888 (Figs 20, 21). *Amphipyra occithianshanica* **sp. n.** is rather similar to the latter one with its light, shining brownish suffused forewings but the double dark brown points of the reniform stigma and the single one of the orbicular stigma are present and well visible, like in *A. tragopoginis*, from which the new species differs in the much lighter forewings. In the male genitalia, the new species (Figs 39, 40) shows

more affinities to *A. turcomana* (Figs 41, 42) but differs from it by the less concave ventral-medial section of the valvae with less broad cucullus, and the much longer dorsal medial extension of the deltoid juxta. In the aedeagus, the ventral carinal plate of the new species is much larger than in *A. turcomana*. In the vesica of *A. occithianshanica* **sp. n.**, the subbasal diverticulum is smaller and less prominent, and the terminal diverticulum has a much larger and denser bundle and cover of hair-like spiculi with different lengths than in *A. turcomana*, besides the long, arched spines. The male genitalia of the new species are more distinctive from *A. tragopoginis* (Figs 37, 38) since it has shorter uncus, and much longer dorso-medial extension of the less deltoid juxta. In the vesica of *A. occithianshanica* **sp. n.**, the subbasal diverticulum is significantly smaller, the terminal diverticulum bearing a much larger and denser bundle and cover of hair-like spiculi with different length (besides the long arched spines), while the terminal diverticulum is practically naked from the small hair like spiculi in *A. tragopoginis*. However, the female genitalia of *A. occithianshanica* **sp. n.** (Fig. 51) are more similar to those of *A. tragopoginis* (Fig. 50). The new species has much larger appendix bursae than in *A. turcomana* (Figs 52, 53) (which has a very small appendix bursae), and significantly longer apophyses anteriores and posteriores and somewhat longer ductus bursae than in *A. tragopoginis* (Fig. 50).

Description. (Figs 18, 19) Medium-sized species, with a wingspan 30–34 mm. Antennae filiform in both sexes. Head and thorax brown. Forewing monochromatic light shining greyish-brown, suffused with blackish scales. Wing pattern reduced; only the sinuous, ribbon-like, conspicuously darker, greyish-brown subterminal field visible, while the orbicular and reniform stigmata being marked with one single and one double dots. Hindwing light unicolorous greyish brown, with obscure darker discal spot, the marginal area slightly broadly darker and darker suffused. The underside of wings shining, whitish-greyish.

Male genitalia (Figs 39, 40). Uncus long, elongate spatulate. Vinculum rather short, v-shaped. Valva evenly curved dorsad, cucullus strongly broaden and hairy. Juxta deltoid, with long dorso-medial extension. Aedeagus broad, curved ventrad, carinal bar broadly sclerotized. Vesica bears two diverticuli, from which the subbasal dorsal one rather small, and tongue-like, while the terminal diverticulum globular with a dense cover of short, hair-like spiculi and a few much stronger and longer spines.

Female genitalia. (Fig. 51). Papillae anales elongate, apically rounded. Apophyses posteriores and anteriores very long and slim, while the apophyses anteriores much shorter. Antrum funnel-like. Ductus bursae short, posteriorly broaden. Appendix bursae long, less prominent, terminally broaden, and angular. Corpus bursae elongated-saccate, strongly curved and tapering terminally.

Distribution and biology. The new species is known only from the western Thian Shan.

Etymology. The name of the new species is after its distribution, since it was found only in the western Thian Shan.

Remark. It is worth mentioning that all the dissected specimens from the western Thian Shan belong to the new species, while all the externally similar dissected male and female specimens from the other parts of Uzbekistan and from Tajikistan and NE Iran proved to be *A. turcomana* and only in one case *A. tragopoginis*.

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Figures 1–8. *Amphipyra* spp. and ssp. adults. **1.** *A. huilini* **sp. n.**, HT, m, China, Sichuan, GYP 5953; **2.** *A. joelmineti* Ronkay & Ronkay, 2023, m, China, Hunan, GYP 5951; **3.** *A. perflua sichuana* **ssp. n.**, HT, m, China, Sichuan, GYP 5947; **4.** *A. perflua sichuana* **ssp. n.**, PT, f, China, Gansu, GYP 5947; **5.** *A. perflua* (Fabricius, 1787), m, N Hungary, Jósvalfő; **6.** *A. perflua* (Fabricius, 1787), f, N Hungary, Jósvalfő; **7.** *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.**, m, PT, China, N Yunnan, 5 km SE of Deqin, RL 9977; **8.** *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.**, m, PT, China, N Yunnan, 5 km SE of Deqin.

Figures 9–21. *Amphipyra* spp. adults. **9.** *A. yunnannocturna* sp. n., f, HT, China, N Yunnan, GYP 5936; **10.** *A. charon* Draudt, 1950, HT, f, China, Hunan, ZFMK; **11.** *A. charon* Draudt, 1950, HT, f, ZFMK, labels; **12.** *A. yunnannocturna* sp. n., f, PT, China, prov. Sichuan, GYP 5937; **13.** *A. meridionalis* sp. n., HT, m, Iran, Zaghros, GYP 2370; **14.** *A. meridionalis* sp. n., PT, f, Iran, Zaghros, GYP 2567; **15.** *A. meridionalis* sp. n., PT, f, Iran, Busher, GYP 5938; **16.** *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759), m, Hungary, Bükk Mts.; **17.** *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759), f, Hungary, Nyékládháza; **18.** *A. occithianshanica* sp. n., HT, m, Uzbekistan, W. Thian Shan, GYP 2121; **19.** *A. occithianshanica* sp. n., PT, f, Uzbekistan, W Thian Shan, GYP 5977; **20.** *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888, m, Uzbekistan, Samarkand, GYP 5955; **21.** *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888, f, Iran, Khorasan, GYP 2722.

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Figure 22. Type locality of *A meridionalis* **sp. n.**, Iran, prov. Boyerahmad-va-Kohgiluyeh, SE-Zagros, 3000 m, Kuh-e-Dena, n. Bijan pass (expedition P. Gyulai & A. Garai)

Figures 23–26. *Amphipyra* spp. male genitalia. **23, 24.** *A. huilini* **sp. n.**, HT, China, Sichuan, GYP 5953; **25, 26.** *A. joelmineti* Ronkay & Ronkay, 2023, China, Hunan, GYP 5951.

Figures 27–34. *Amphipyra* spp. and ssp. male genitalia. **27, 28.** *A. perflua sichuana* **ssp. n.**, HT, China, Sichuan, GYP 5947; **29, 30.** *A. perflua sichuana* **ssp. n.**, PT, China, Gansu, GYP 5995; **31, 32.** *A. perflua* (Fabricius, 1787), N Hungary, Jósvalfő, GYP 5973; **33, 34.** *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.**, PT, China, N Yunnan, RL 9977.

Figures 35–42. *Amphipyra* spp. male genitalia. **35, 36.** *A. meridionalis* sp. n., HT, Iran, Zaghros, Dena, GYP 2370; **37, 38.** *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759), Hungary, Klementina, GYP 5943; **39, 40.** *A. occithianshanica* sp. n., HT, Uzbekistan, Thian Shan, GYP 2121; **41, 42.** *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888, Uzbekistan, Samarkand, GYP 5955.

Figures 43–48. *Amphipyra* spp. and ssp. female genitalia. **43.** *A. perflua sichuana* **ssp. n.**, PT, China, Gansu, GYP 5959; **44.** *A. perflua* (Fabricius, 1787), N Hungary, Jósvalfő, GYP 5974; **45.** *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.**, PT, China, N Yunnan, GYP 5936; **46.** *A. yunnannocturna* **sp. n.**, PT, China, Sichuan, GYP 5937; **47.** *A. charon* Draudt, 1950, PT, China, Hunan, HM 8391, ZFMK; **48.** *A. meridionalis* **sp. n.**, PT, Iran, Busher, GYP 5938.

Figures 49–53. *Amphipyra* spp. female genitalia. **49.** *A. meridionalis* **sp. n.**, PT, Iran, Zaghros, GYP 2567; **50.** *A. tragopoginis* (Clerck, 1759) Hungary, Bükk Mts., GYP 5942; **51.** *A. occithianshanica* **sp. n.**, PT, Uzbekistan, W Thian Shan, GYP 5977; **52.** *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888, Iran, Khorasan, GYP 2722; **53.** *A. turcomana* Staudinger, 1888, Tajikistan, Dushanbe, GYP 2572.

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